

Tests of Accelerated Ageing of Composite Materials in Shipbuilding

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Summary

In nautical technology, the newness of material (absence of information on long-term behaviour) and the lack of knowledge concerning the actual demands applied to a marine structure, lead designers to make use of composite materials with high safety factors.

Judging the functioning of materials on a long-term basis involves establishing strict test protocols for accelerated ageing. These enable physical or chemical degradations of the materials to be detected (plastifications, swelling, hydrolysis), life-span provision to be made and materials to be classified.

The aim of this experimental simulation is to compare the accelerated ageing under load of several laminates submerged in water at a temperature of about 70°C.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mechanical reaction of long fibre composites with a polymere matrix is closely linked to the mechanical and physical proprieties of the matrix. A polymere matrix composite is therefore, like its polymere matrix, particularly sensitive to environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity or ultra-violet rays.

[1] [2] [3]

One of the main obstacles to the penetration of composites into the mechanical industry sector, is the lack of basic information concerning their hygrothermomechanical properties under semi-static or dynamic regime. Indeed, in most structural applications, the materials are subject to stress characterized by the temporal evolution of the group of mechanical and physico-chemical parametes (heat or mass transfes). The reaction of the materials is therefore a complex combination of reactions of a purely mechanical, physico-chemical or thermic nature. [4]

2. PRINCIPLE OF BEHAVIOUR

In order to broach the complex reaction of structures subject to a hygrothermomechanical environment, simplifying hypotheses must be introduced. Therefore,

from now on, the following hypotheses will be retained to develop an experimental model of the reaction of composite materials in a hygrothermomechanical environment : [1]

- the material is taxed in its elasticity range and is orthotropic,
- the fibre is flexible, globally homogeneous and non-absorbant in most cases,
- the matrix is flexible, homogeneous and absorbant,
- fibre-matrix adherence is perfect,
- in the case of laminates, contact between layers is perfect,

the theoreme is :

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^0 + C_{ij}^{\text{kl}} \varepsilon_{\text{kl}} - \alpha_{ij} (T - T_0) - \beta_{ij} (H - H_0) \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \varepsilon_{ij}^0 + S_{ij}^{\text{kl}} \sigma_{\text{kl}} - \alpha_i (T - T_0) \delta_{ij} - \beta_{ij} (H - H_0) \quad (2)$$

$\sigma_{ij}^0, \varepsilon_{ij}^0$: pre-stressing and initial deformations

α_{ij} : thermic modules

β_{ij} : hygrometric modules

α_i : thermal expansion coefficient (with $\alpha_1 = \alpha_{11}$, si $ij = 11$ etc,...)

β_1 : hygrometric expansion coefficient

Solving the hygrothermomechanical problem requires the introduction of supplementary hypotheses referring to the decoupling of the thermic and hygrometric effects.

$$\begin{aligned} q_i^{(T)} &= K_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \\ q_i^{(H)} &= D_{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x_j} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $q(T)$ and $q(H)$ are respectively the heat flow and hygrometric vectors
 K_{ij} and D_{ij} are the diffusion and conduction coefficient.

From a practical point of view, this means characterizing the material thermically and so determining α_{ij} , followed by a mechanical characterization under tension to calculate the properties of elasticity S_{ijkl} ; the results and the experimental methods used will be given later.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SIMULATION

The loading method chosen is that of 4 point flexion which has the advantage of being easily set up and causing less local degradation than 3 point tests.

3.1 : Presentation of the test-bench : A multicellular loading bench enables the simultaneous loading, by four point flexion, of test samples. the complete set is placed in a tank filled with demineralised water so as to carry out submersion test. A water heater ensures that the temperature of the demineralised water remains constant (70°C for the purposes of our study). Each test sample has a displacement sensor for studying the evolution of its deflection.

The load applied to each test sample is 207 Newton. This figure takes into account the forces induced by the various elements of the bench. The load intensity has been chosen so as to apply 25% breakage stress to the materials tested.

Information obtained on a permanent basis by means of a UPM 60 measuring system. The need to store and process the information files has led to the development of acquisition software enabling experimentation to be carried out almost autonomously. Twenty test samples are fitted with extensometer gauges enabling the thermal (expansion factor α_1 and β_1) and mechanical characterisation of the materials (modules : E_1 and Poisson ratio ν_1). Then test samples are protected (M Coat JL) in such a way that they absorb water only on the

upper surface , the parameters followed during these flow test are : the deflection $W(t)$, the longitudinal strain $\epsilon_1(t)$ and the transversal strain $\epsilon_2(t)$, the Young modulus $E_1(t)$. The longitudinal stress $\sigma_1(t)$ is deduced from the longitudinal strain and the Young modulus $E_1(t)$, while the diffusion factor D_1 is deduced from the equation (7)

4. MATERIAL USED

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Fibres	Glass fabric E 830 g/m ² two- leaf+will warp at 0° weft at 90°	Glass fabric E 830 g/m ² two- leaf+will warp at 0° weft at 90°	Glass fabric E 830 g/m ² two- leaf+will warp at 0° weft at 90°	Glass fabric E 1040 g/m ² satin 8 wharp at 0° weft at 90°	Glass fabric E 1040 g/m ² satin 8 wharp at 0° weft at 90°	double skew 1060 gr/m ² (0,+45) Glass fabricE	Blended fabric Intra- foldGlass E-Kevlar 900gr/m ² wharp at 0°	Blended fabric Intra-fold GlassE/Kev 500gr/m ² nudirection al
Resin	Polyester isophthalique	Vinylester	Epoxy Epicote 815	Vinylester Hallowglas Microballs 0=10 to 50 µ	Vinylester Hallowglas Microballs 0=10 to 50 µ	Vinylester	Vinylester	Vinylester
com po si t e s	8 folds oriented at 0° 48% glass 52% resin (in weight) surface Mass 13,86 kg/m ²	8 folds oriented at 0° 48% glass 52% resin (in weight) surface Mass 13,06 kg/m ²	8 folds oriented at 0° 45,8% glass 54,2% resin (in weight) surface Mass 13,92 kg/m ²	6 folds oriented at 0° 54,5% glass 39,5% resin+6% µ balls (in weight) surface Mass 11,46 kg/m ²	6 folds oriented at 0° 53,3% glass 40% resin +6,7 % µballs (in weight) surface Mass 11,k/m ²	16 folds oriented at 0° 63,8% glass 30,2 % resin (in weight) surface Mass 16,74 kg/m ²	10 folds oriented at 0° 40,1% glass 35 % resin 24,9 kevlar (in weight) surface Mass 13,84 kg/m ²	8 folds oriented at 0° 34% glass 47 % resin 19 % kevlar (in weight) surface Mass 15 kg/m ²
Thickness	from 8,5 to 9,1 mm	from 8,6 to 9,6 mm	from 8,5 to 9,8 mm	from 10 to 12 mm	from 10 to 12 mm	from 10 to 12 mm	from 9 to 9,5 mm	from 9 to 12 mm

Table (1) Characteristics of the different materials studied

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

5.1 Thermal expansion factors

Sample	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	σ
α_1 10-6/°c	26,6	23,7	12,2	13,8	17,8	10,5	9,4	1,7	1,18
α_1 10-6/°c	20,7	16	18,2	17,8	23,3	28,2	11,5	25,8	3,3

Table(2) α_1 and α_2 for the materials used , σ : typical difference

5.2 Elasticity characteristics:

Sample	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	σ
E1 MPa	15232	17637	16546	12103	12533	31548	32051	32284	1,2
ν_{12}	0,103	0,135	0,118	0,148	0,122	0,393	0,092	0,591	0,02

Table(3) : E1, ν_{12} for differents materials

5.3 Test on ageing of the materials and results

5.3.1 four point flexion

figure 2: four point flexion test bench

Deflection tracked by means of displacement sensors . The measure is relative (measure of W) . Given this , it is possible to follow an evolution of the Young module E1 . This depends on the time E1(t) since we are adopting the hypothesis of ageing .

The deflection equation corresponding to the current setup for the measure of W is defined by :

$$W(x,t) = P. a (Lx - x^2 - a^2/3)/(2E(t) I) \quad (4)$$

I : quadruc moment .

Relation (4) given :

$$E(t) W(L/2,t) = \text{cnst} . \quad (5)$$

Working with (5) enables the evolution of module E1 to be followed and time controlled .

$$E(t) W(L/2,t) = E(0) W(L/2,0) \quad (6)$$

6 .INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

SampleP3 : The sample broke after 12 hours , the parallel tests on water absorption showing that when the material ruptured , the quantity of water absorbed was about 0,1% figure4 , the examination of deflection and of elasticity the module E1 (figure 7 and 9) shows a change of gradient in the variation of these two parameter according to time in the region of 4 hours . This change in gradient is repeated on the deformation ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 (figure 6) which show simultaneously the effects of flow (change of speed) and the expansion effects observed ϵ_2 t=0 to 12 hours (effect of water absorption).

The instantaneous stress $\sigma_1(t)$ figure 10 is defined by :

$$\sigma_1(t) = E_1(t) \epsilon_1(t) \tag{8}$$

showing an increasing evolution of t=0 to 6 hours where it reaches a maximum corresponding to the ruin of the sample .

FIG 5

FIG 6

FIG 7

FIG 8

FIG 9

FIG 10

5.3.2 Kinetic absorption

The determination of the water absorption kinetics was carried out by measuring weigh-gain . To do this scales with 1/10000 g accuracy were used.

In order to reduce errors to a minimum and obtain the best repetitiveness the following procedure has been developed : the test samples are :

- taken out of the bath ,
- dried in an oven at 70°C for 5 minutes,
- dried and returned to the surrounding temperature in a deshumidifier for an hour ,
- weighed ,
- returned to the bath.

The fick model is used to exact D1 and M∞. For a panel which is insulated around the edges , the exploitation of the linear field gives :

$$M(t)/M_{\infty} = (4/s) \sqrt{(D t) / \pi} \quad (7)$$

S= 2h for a panel which is absorbant on one surface only ,

M(t)= [(weight of the material at t) - (initial weight)]/(initial weight of then material)

M∞= percentage of water absorbed at saturation ,

D= diffusion factor ,

h = thickness of the panel .

t= time

5.3.3 Results

Figure 2: Deflection according to time

Figure 3: Young Module according to time

Figure 4: Water Diffusion

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{2 M_{\infty}} \right)^2 \frac{(M_2 - M_1)^2}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \quad , D \text{ en } \text{mm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$$

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P8
h (mm)	7,8	7,1	7,8	11,8	11,8	9,3	9,5
M% satur.	2,3	3,8	4,6	8,5	8,5	4,0	7,0
M1%	0,07	0,69	0,75	1,12	0,99	0,36	1,09
M2%	1,59	2,59	2,78	5,24	6,06	3,29	4,48
t1 (h)	24	144	144	144	144	168	312
t2 (h)	384	648	648	1056	1848	1680	1512
D(10 ⁻⁴ mm ² / s)	2,68	1,52	1,43	1,70	1,13	1,29	1,03

The analysis of the properties of materials P1,P2,P4,P5,P6, and P8 enables the following comments to be made :
 The flow in the primary zone $0 \leq t \leq 500$ hours $w(t)$ and $E1(t)$ varies very rapidly and 50 to 75 % of the material's performance is lost .

Specimen		P1	P2	P4	P5	P6	P8
t=0	Wmm	0,400	0,470	0,195	0,09	0,187	0,098
	ϵ 1MPa	22968	17525	11251	12502	26830	23587
t=500 hours	Wmm	1,2	0,8	0,65	0,3	0,26	0,34
	E1 MPa	5000	9500	2800	5000	13000	8800

Table(4) characteristics of the materials after 500 hours

Beyond this , a secondary flow zone can be distinguished in which the speed is slower (zone2) . Then zone 3 : the zone in which the flow speed remains steady (tertiary zone) and lastly zone 4 : the zone in which the flow speed increases rapidly to produce breakage .

Analysis of the cliches under electronic microscope concerns three zones on graded sample .

figure12 loading bench

- zone 1 : cross-section along an upper support ,
- zone 2 : cross-section at a distance of $x= 15$ mm from an upper support
- zone 3 : cross-section in the middle of the supports .

Observation of photographs of the unspoilt material (figure 12) shows up the following faults

-The presence of bubbles in the resin ; these bubbles represent favourable places for retaining water . The solvent pockets thus created then provoke pressure which can begin cracking in the resin or help rupture the fibre-matrix bonds.

-bad coherence of the fibre-matrix interface mainly attributed to development procedures. The presence of these initial delaminations can act as a water penetration route .

Examination of the breakage pattern figure(13 to 16) shows that the cohesion losses cracks are produced mainly on the upper surface (surface subject to compression) , the initial faults and micro-buckling of the reinforcement under the stress of compression can explain the propagation of cracks and the delaminations as well as the effects of the water on the acceleration of this test sample .

- differential dilatation (effect of temperature)
- mechanical load (traction -compression or shearing)
- initial defects (development)
- hygrometric load (demineralised water)

sem to have this material very severely , and this raises the problem of the representativity test in these conditions .

specimen flawless- magnification
Fig 13

specimen damaged-magnification 150 zone 1
Fig 14

specimen damaged-magnification 45
Fig 15 zone 3

specimen damaged -magnification 1000
Fig 16 zone 2

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